

Evaluation based on rubrics and learning outcomes in the subject Systems of Representation

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Abstract — In the subject “Systems of Representation” of the programme of the School of Architecture La Salle we apply a rubric-based evaluation system to assess student learning. The rubric is jointly designed with the learning activity. Our experience of applying rubrics to learning outcomes in recent years has revealed both potential and limitations. Based on this experience, enhancements to make the current evaluation procedures more effective are proposed.

Keywords – Bologna process; architectural education; learning outcomes; rubrics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Systems of Representation (SDR, *Sistemas de Representación*, in Spanish) is part of the undergraduate programme in Architecture at La Salle Campus Barcelona. Continuing with the pedagogic line established by the basic courses of the Bauhaus and Vkhutemas schools, the purpose of SDR is to develop the students’ capacity to perceive and represent form and space, capacities that are not specific to architectural education but also essential to any form-giving creative activity [1]. Besides dealing with the basics of form and space, colour and materials in three-dimensional and two-dimensional works, SDR includes other topics such as graphic design and typography, audio-visual communication and image technologies (video, photography). Likewise, SDR promotes the combined use of digital tools –word processing, design and layout, drawing and modelling, rendering, image processing and animation– with manual techniques –sketching, physical modelling–.

More than a subject in the traditional sense, SDR is a learning space in which knowledge is constructed by interlinking different subject-matters: art and architecture, aesthetics and composition, graphic design and visual communication (Fig. 1). The multiple relationships between these subjects give rise to a space of knowledge that transcends the boundaries of each individual matter. In this open and multidisciplinary learning space, knowledge is essentially a collaborative construction carried out by teachers and students.

Figure 1. SDR: a space for the construction of transdisciplinary knowledge

Some of the topics that are integrated in SDR are also dealt with in other subjects of the curriculum, such as Graphic Expression, Descriptive Geometry, Computer Tools, History and Composition. With regard to these other subjects, SDR offers an opportunity to apply the knowledge that students have acquired in these subjects in a relational learning space. In the classroom, contents are presented in a relational way, linking some topics with others. For instance, colour theory is explained in relation to composition and computer graphics; visual composition is related to musical composition, and concrete art painting to Gestalt psychology. This relational thinking is also applied by the students in the learning activities that they carry out. For example, they produce a computer animation based on the interpretation of a concrete art work and a musical composition.

SDR adheres to the constructivist pedagogy that places the student at the centre of the learning (*student-centred teaching and learning*). Therefore, a part of our pedagogic work is to design the learning environments in which students will develop their knowledge-construction processes (*learning design*). In the design of the learning activities we take into account the processes, materials and resources required to achieve the learning outcomes. These activities are structured in sequences (*learning sequences*) and are carried out individually and in collaboration (Fig. 2). Along these sequences, the outcome of a learning activity might become the starting point of the next one. This may imply, for example, the translation (i.e. transposition or transference) of an idea from a system of representation to

another: translating a text to a multimedia presentation; a physical model to a digital one –or vice versa–; a photograph to a narrative; or the experience of a space in a space represented in a video. In this way, the sequences of activities connected to each other facilitate a learning process that each student adapts to his or her interests and capabilities.

Figure 2. Learning activities of the theme OBJECT structured as sequences

The activities can be of different kinds (writing, drawing, modelling, filming, photographing, etc.) and they can be performed in class or outside, individually or in teams. All activities are uploaded to the web-based learning system SDR : NET, specifically created to support the pedagogic model (Fig. 3). Some of the learning activities are performed directly in this environment, where students’ works become another learning resource: commenting and evaluating other students’ work, grouping and relating contents, searching for references, etc.

Figure 3. Presentation of an exercise on SDR : NET corresponding to the first stage of the sequence “Object and Form”

The blended-learning model fostered by SDR encompasses classroom activities –mainly dedicated to presenting the topics to be reflected upon, explaining ideas and concepts and discussing them with the students– and the work done on the on-line environment SDR : NET. Teachers –acting as *learning designers*– create the sequences of learning activities and

connect them to the resources (readings, references) that students need for carrying out their work. Through SDR : NET, students’ works are available for the whole class. In this way, students contribute to creating educational resources to be used for new learning activities (*resource-based learning*). For example, to evaluate and comment on the work of other students; to create relationships between different students’ works; or to group those that have some features in common. Works created by students are also related to the resources provided by teachers, thus facilitating the collective construction of a relational knowledge in which students and teachers participate.

II. FROM THE INSTRUCTION PARADIGM TO THE LEARNING PARADIGM: THE BOLOGNA MODEL

In the Bologna declaration of 1999, the EU member states expressed their commitment to creating a European area of higher education, which would require the adoption of “a system of easily readable and comparable degrees”, based on two main cycles –undergraduate and graduate–, with a shared evaluation system of ECTS credits. Later on, in the Berlin Communiqué of 2013 [2], there was a more precise reference to the evaluation system, whose purpose would be “to elaborate a framework of comparable and compatible qualifications for their higher education systems, which should seek to describe qualifications in terms of workload, level, learning outcomes, competences and profile”. This explicit reference to learning outcomes and competencies represents a qualitative change with regard to the original Bologna declaration, in so far it assumes a student-centred education model which focuses on learning as opposed to a content-based education focused on teaching [3].

While certain aspects of the education model supported by the Bologna process –such as the two-cycle system– have gradually been implemented by universities in Europe –albeit not without difficulties, especially in the schools of architecture in Spain– the application of an evaluation system focused on learning outcomes still remains a big challenge for many institutions. In a competency-based curriculum, learning activities are designed around a set of key competences, that is, the knowledge, skills and attitudes that students will acquire in the learning process. This means rethinking the whole curriculum, either to adapt it to the new model or to create a new one, an effort which not all schools are willing to make.

At the outset, one of the difficulties in the design and implementation of a competence-based model stems from the confusion of the terms involved. Even today, the distinction between competences, skills, learning objectives, learning outcomes and assessment criteria is not always clear to those educators in charge of designing and applying a student-centred model. In order to clarify the diverse meanings of some of these terms, the European Qualification Framework [4] provides the following definitions:

- ‘learning outcomes’ means statements of what a learner knows, understands and is able to do on completion of a learning process, which are defined in terms of knowledge, skills and competence;
- ‘knowledge’ means the outcome of the assimilation of information through learning. Knowledge is the body of

facts, principles, theories and practices that is related to a field of work or study

- 'skills' means the ability to apply knowledge and use know-how to complete tasks and solve problems. They can be cognitive (involving the use of logical, intuitive and creative thinking) or practical (involving manual dexterity and the use of methods, materials, tools and instruments)
- 'competence' means the proven ability to use knowledge, skills and personal, social and/or methodological abilities, in work or study situations and in professional and personal development.

Further distinctions between these terms have been discussed by educationalists. For Watson (2002), a learning outcome is "something that students can do now that they could not do previously ... a change in people as a result of a learning experience". Hartel and Foegeding [5], have distinguished between "competency," "learning objective," and "learning outcome". According to these authors, "competency" refers to "a general statement detailing the desired knowledge and skills of student graduating from our course or program"; "learning objective" is "a very general statement about the larger goals of the course or program"; and "learning outcome" is "a very specific statement that describes exactly what a student will be able to do in some measurable way". They conclude that "the main distinction between objective or competency and a true learning outcome is that a learning outcome is written so that it can be measured or assessed." In a similar vein, Hussey and Smith [6] observed that "Our objectives can be identified with our expected learning outcomes, but what we observe in our assessments are our actual learning outcomes" which are "precise, explicit and objectively measurable". For other authors, however, the terms "learning objective" and "learning outcome" are interchangeable [7] [8].

Competencies, learning objectives and/or learning outcomes are strongly intertwined in a competence-based curriculum design. The assessment of the student learning, within each module or course, should be aligned with the desired learning objectives. According to Biggs [9], this "constructive alignment" means that "the teaching methods used and the assessment tasks, are aligned with the learning activities assumed in the intended outcomes learning activities appropriate to achieving the desired learning outcomes". However, "[this alignment] would appear to be an obvious criterion, if it were not a fact that in practice it is frequently not the case. How to get the assessment right, i.e. in line with the learning objectives or at least as right as possible, should be a major concern in any approach to assessment." [8].

The adoption of a student-centred model of education conveys an evaluation based on the learning outcomes, which puts the focus on the students' achievements. In this regard, the work done in a module or unit, and on the whole programme, should contribute to the student's acquisition of a set of competences that s/he will apply in the professional world.

III. LEARNING OUTCOMES AND RUBRICS

Some criteria need to be established to assess to which extent the work done by a student meets the expected learning outcomes [10]. Typically, rubrics are used for this purpose. Allen and Tanner [11] define rubric as "a type of matrix that provides scaled levels of achievement or understanding for a set of criteria or dimensions of quality for a given type of performance". The meaning of the evaluation with rubrics is not so much to grade the students' work as to provide a meaningful feedback which helps the student to progress in the learning. Typically, a rubric includes, in various formats, the following components: learning outcomes, assessment criteria, level descriptors and rating scale. Rubrics enable teachers (and also students) to assess the level of competency achieved in the execution of particular learning activity which helps the student to progress on the path towards the acquisition the learning outcomes of the whole undergraduate programme. There are "analytic" rubrics, which measure diverse elements within a task, and "holistic" rubrics to make an overall assessment of the student output.

However, the evaluation based on learning outcomes has certain limitations. The specification of the learning outcomes to be achieved can constrain the learning experience, since "there is a danger that learning outcomes become the driver of classroom interactions and prevent discussion of ideas or questions that do not clearly relate to the set outcomes for the course/module" [12]. Also, an overly explicit description of the objectives to be achieved "fails to grasp is that any worthwhile learning has elements of uncertainty, which makes pre-specification in terms of deterministic behavioural or near-behavioural objectives impossible" [8]. In their critique to learning outcomes, Hussey and Smith made three objections: firstly, it is "it is neither practical nor useful to try to specify learning outcomes with the kind of precision", since no matter how detailed the description is, it will always require an interpretation which will rely on the knowledge of the interpreter, student or teacher; secondly, they are "insensitive to the requirements of different disciplines", because a learning outcome described with the same words would have a different value for one or another discipline; and thirdly, even if students would be able to interpret them properly, providing the previous two limitations, "they may actually restrict the subsequent educational outcomes", because students focus on achieving exactly what will be assessed, rather than openly exploring their own paths to acquire knowledge. In order to prevent such risks, learning outcomes should be "understood and interpreted in this more flexible and practical way", so that they do not become an auditing instrument, only [6].

In the field of arts education, and architecture can be considered part of it, it is not always feasible –nor desirable – to measure learning outcomes in subjects which involve "the development of intuition, inventiveness, imagination, visualisation, risk-taking, etc." [13]. In particular, visualization is a fundamental cognitive ability for any student in the field, which is difficult to assess in quantitative terms. As Davies argues, even though art students need to know what they are expected to learn, this does not have to be communicated necessarily through declarative learning outcomes. Rather, there are other personalized ways –tutoring, crits, examples– to

communicate them. Lastly, one more difficulty to apply learning outcomes in art education is that students' works are "projects" which cannot be analysed in parts, but evaluated as wholes.

IV. APPLICATION OF THE EVALUATION SYSTEM BASED ON LEARNING OUTCOMES IN THE SUBJECT SYSTEMS OF REPRESENTATION

In accordance with the principles of a competence-based curriculum, the evaluation of the activities in SDR is aligned (Fig. 4) with the (1) knowledge and skills that an architect is expected to demonstrate in practice, (2) the competences the students need to acquire in the studies, (3) the learning outcomes to achieve in the activities carried out on our subject, and (4) the rubric use to assess them. Ideally, there should be a continuous alignment between these four levels, in both top-down and bottom-up directions. This means, for example, that the experience of applying a rubric to evaluate a task might lead to reviewing the learning outcomes of the overall subject, and this in turn might affect the list of competences of the overall curriculum. Conversely, a change in the professional qualifications of architects might lead to a review of the curricular competences of the programme, and this in turn would have an impact on the learning outcomes.

Figure 4. Learning activities of the theme OBJECT structured as sequences

A. Professional qualifications

The contents and learning activities of SDR contribute to the acquisitions of four of the eleven "knowledge and skills" which architects should have according to the EU 2005/36/EC [14] directive about professional qualifications, in particular these four:

1. An ability to create architectural designs that satisfy both aesthetic and technical requirements;
2. An adequate knowledge of the history and theories of architecture and the related arts, technologies and human sciences;
3. A knowledge of the fine arts as an influence on the quality of architectural design;

6. An understanding of the profession of architecture and the role of the architect in society, in particular in preparing briefs that take account of social factors.

B. Competences (programme level)

In a study carried out with as part of the elaboration of a guide to evaluate competences in engineering and architecture [15] for the higher education institutions in Catalonia, we created a map of the competences of the curriculum of the School of Architecture La Salle with the collaboration of representatives of the various subjects included in the programme. In the proposed competence-based programme we elaborated as an example for this guide, the listed competences cut across the subjects and curriculum levels. This way, it was possible to measure to which extent a particular competence was endorsed by various subjects throughout the different levels of the academic programme. According to the proposed model, SDR would contribute to the acquisition of the following competences, organized into instrumental, interpersonal and systemic:

1) Instrumental competences:

- Capacity for analysis and synthesis
- Basic general knowledge about study area
- Oral and written communication on one's own language
- Knowledge of a second language
- Basic skills in the use of computer
- Skills on information management
- Basic and fundamental knowledge of the field of training

2) Interpersonal competences:

- Capacity for criticism and self-criticism
- Teamwork

3) Systemic competences:

- Research skills
- Ability to learn
- Ability to generate new ideas (creativity)
- Ability to work in a way autonomous

This list of competences, prepared for the model proposed for the guide, is still the reference framework for the design and evaluation of the activities that are carried out in SDR.

C. Learning outcomes (course level)

Learning outcomes in this subject are described taking into account the competences that the graduate is expected to acquire on the programme and which s/he will later apply in their professional practice (Table I).

TABLE I. EXAMPLES OF LEARNING OUTCOMES

Learning outcomes
Ability to understand the critical framework of contemporary architecture
Ability to perceive and represent architectural space with various techniques (drawing, photography, video)
Ability to compose elements in space, in various media (graphic design, composition, photography,...)
Ability to use modelling techniques which suit the formal properties of the designed object
Ability to represent a form generation process in an intelligible and personal manner

D. Rubric

Learning activities are described in a standardized format, including the following items:

- Name of the theme
- Name of the activity
- Description
- Objectives
- Learning outcomes
- Assignment
- Rubric
- Recommendations

The analytic rubric is designed to evaluate the outcome of each learning activity, in its different dimensions. For instance, a rubric for a learning activity dedicated to taking photographs of the city to convey an idea contained in a textual reference provided would include three dimensions: Reflecting, Photographing and Writing (Table II).

TABLE II. ALIGNMENT OF LEARNING OUTCOMES, RUBRIC AND ASSESSEMENT CRITERIA

Learning outcome	Learning activity Photographing the city to convey a concept from a textual reference	
	Rubric	
	Dimensions	Assessment criteria
Ability to understand the critical framework of contemporary architecture	<i>Reflecting:</i> To demonstrate a capacity to further elaborate the ideas contained in the reference texts, and to relate them to the images.	The student has identified relevant references which reflect issues debated in contemporary debate; the student has understood the contribution of an architectural project to the current debate, the student has derived proper conclusions of the reference texts.
Ability to perceive and represent architectural space with various techniques (drawing, photography, video)	<i>Photographing:</i> To be able to capture in a photograph the spatial qualities (atmosphere, perspective, boundaries); framing and viewpoint (pictorial representation of space); aesthetics (adherence to recognized styles, originality);	The student is able to capture the qualities of a space in a photography of an urban landscape

	lighting (diffused, contrasted, etc.).	
Ability to write (in own's language or in English) meaningful and intelligible texts which are the expression of the student's own thoughts	<i>Writing:</i> To write intelligible, correct and expressive texts describing the relationships between the content of the readings and the photograph	The student is able to describe the relationships between the ideas derived from the readings and the idea of the city captured in the photographic image, unveiling the meanings that are in both, and interrelating them in a personal manner.

Each dimension is described in a simple a concise manner, in a language that the student can understand. Furthermore, each dimension of the rubric is aligned with one (or more) of the learning outcomes that students are expected to achieve in the subject. These explicit descriptions of the assessment criteria are shared with students, and used to set up a shared criterion among the various teachers to evaluate the students' outputs. We avoid level descriptors because past experience has shown that they tend to be counterproductive and hinder the development of works which, in most cases, are the outcome of a creative process. The elements of the rubric are assessed with the same grading scale that is used in all the subjects, from 0 to 10, with a 5 for pass.

The evaluation of the work of students is done on a continuous basis. The rubrics of all learning activities carried out in a theme are compiled in an Excel document which is also used to introduce the grades. Each dimension of the rubric has a weight in the final grade of a learning activity. For instance, if the activity is fundamentally visual, the dimension "composition" has more weight than the dimension "writing". In turn, each learning activity has a different weight in the overall grade. Complex activities which combine multiple skills and require more time have more weight than a short activity done in class. Participation in class activities is also considered (30% of the final grade). However, a student is unlikely to fail as a result of poor participation in class. The weighting percentages of learning activities is not disclosed to the students, to prevent them prioritizing one activity over another.

V. REFLECTIONS AND FURTHER WORK

Currently, the school's academic programme is not based on a competence-based curriculum. The competences we are using are those included in the evaluation guide of 2009. In the meantime, the school did not change its academic programme into a competence-based curriculum. The application of the evaluation based on learning outcomes is done in some of the subjects and it is left to the criterion of the teachers.

For practical reasons, we found it necessary to minimize the extra load that an evaluation based on learning outcomes represents, for teachers and students. With this purpose, we have reduced the rubric to the minimum elements. However, certain enhancements are necessary to make the current evaluation system an effective tool to support learning. A rubric should serve as a communication channel between students and teachers, in both directions, something that it is not happening at

the moment. This bi-directionality is something we need to support in the future, providing written statements of the assessed dimensions of each task. The communication would take place in the web-based learning environment SDR: NET, which will need to be enhanced to support this functionality. Furthermore, students would appreciate a formative assessment rather than only a summative one. This is particularly important in a subject in which students undertake creative activities, translating ideas from one media onto another, so that new ideas evolve as part of this process. Finally, the engagement of students in the design of the rubrics would be of great benefit. For instance, the dimensions to be assessed and their meaning could be discussed with them, and they could use them for self and peer-evaluation.

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